

Stress and the Entrepreneurship

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Abstract

This paper explores the stress of entrepreneur. Some of the most common entrepreneurial goals are independence, wealth and work satisfaction. Research studies of the entrepreneur shows that though who achieve this goals often pay a high price. A majority of entrepreneurs surveyed had back problems, indigestion, insomnia or headaches. To achieve their goals, however, these entrepreneurs were willing to tolerate these effects of stress. The rewards justified the costs.

Introduction

In general, stress can be viewed function of discrepancies between a person's exception and ability to demands, as well as discrepancies between individual expectations and personality. The person unable to fulfill role demands, then stress occurs to the extent entrepreneurs' work demands and exception exceed their ability to perform to venture initiators, they are likely to experience stress. One researcher has pointed out how entrepreneurial roles and operating environment can lead to stress. Initiating and managing the business require taking significant risk. As previously mentioned, this risk may be described as financial, career, social, family or psychic. Also, entrepreneur must engage in constant, communication activities, interacting with relevant external constituencies including customers, suppliers, lawyers, regulators and accountants, which is stress full.

Characteristics of Entrepreneurial Stress

Chronic and severe sense of time urgency. For instance, type A people become particularly in traffic jams.

Constant involvement multiple projects subject to deadlines. Some how type A people take delight in the feeling of the being swamped with work.

Neglect of all aspects of life except work. These workaholics live to work rather than work to live.

A tendency to take on excessive responsibility, combined with the feelings that "Only I am capable of taking care of this matter."

Sources of Stress

1. Loneliness
2. Immersion In Business
3. People Problem
4. Need To Achieve

1. Loneliness

Although entrepreneurs are usually surrounded by others—employees, customers, accountants and lawyers—they are also isolated from people in whom they can confide.

2. Immersion In Business

They work long hours leaving little time for civic organizations, recreation, or further education.

3. People Problem

Entrepreneurs must depend on and work with partners, employees, customers, bankers and professionals. Most experience frustration, disappointment and aggravation in their experience with this people. Successful entrepreneurs are to some extent perfectionists and know how they want this done.

4. Need To Achieve

Achievement brings satisfaction. During the Boyd and Gumpert study, however, it became clear that a fine line exists between attempting to achieve too much and failing to achieve enough.

Dealing With Stress

- Networking
- Getting Away From It All
- Communicating With Employees
- Finding Satisfaction Outside The Company
- Delegating

1. Networking

One way to relieve the loneliness of running a business is to share experience by networking with other business owners.

2. Getting Away From It All

The best antidote to immersion in business, report many entrepreneurs is a holiday.

3. Communicating With Employees

Entrepreneurs in close contact with employees and can readily access the concerns of their staffs.

4. Finding Satisfaction Outside The Company

Entrepreneurs need to get away from the business occasionally, and they care more passionately about life itself.

5. Delegating

Implementation of coping mechanisms requires implementation time. To gain this time the entrepreneur has to delegate tasks.

Various Problems Inhibiting Entrepreneur

In developing entrepreneurship we are confronted with several problems. These problems as perceived by the personnel engaged in entrepreneurial development are relevant. Because they are experienced by people who encounter these difficulties

- Devotion of organizational skills to areas other than business.
- Customs and tradition of the locality either restricting business or prohibiting it.

- Poor response to monetary incentives.
- Lack status given to business man in the society.
- Lack of adequate infrastructure facilities.
- High cost of production.
- High risk involved new enterprises.
- Market conditions.
- Frequent changes

Entrepreneur and Stress Management

Effective enterprise management means formulating an appropriate business strategy. Through the business strategy, entrepreneurs deliver a message to employees about what is expected of them. A shared business strategy actually means familiarizing yourself with the company's vision of developing. If employees agree with the vision of management and the enterprise they develop the responsibility to take hard, stressful work that is necessary for a creative, risky development of a strategy.⁷ Recognition and control of stress is the basis for the efficient operation of the enterprise because the efficient operation depends on the personal characteristics of the individual such as responsibility, ability to work, the ability to control themselves, and the ability to control the negative feelings that result from the impact of the source of stressful conditions. Predicting future events that can cause stressful situations among employees is an obligation for the entrepreneur. An entrepreneur should have the ability to perceive the real situation in terms of perceiving and controlling stress and affect the reduction of sources of stressful situations among employees.

Conclusion

The purpose of this conceptual analysis was to discuss how role stress can be used in entrepreneurship research. The conceptualization herein provides ample support for the study of role stress in entrepreneurial settings as well as the development of future research agendas. Based on these observations, a sufficient body of psychological and sociological literature exists on outcomes to test causal models and pursue deductive research on entrepreneur role stress. Role stress may help resolving unanswered questions in the field of entrepreneurship, and it has potential to further the research on entrepreneurial identity.

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